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**ENHANCING EFFENCY OF THE CHALLENGE
METHOD IN TEACHING ENGLISH**

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ABSTRACT

The article provides a literary review of effective methods used in teaching English. Today, English is the main tool for access to world-class opportunities. The purpose of the article is to study the features and effectiveness of modern methods in accordance with modern requirements. To identify effective methods for the development of cognitive processes in the training of students. Challenge method is the development of independent decision-making skills, the formation of different - communicative skills in group or individual work in language learning. The effectiveness of the use of the Challenge method in teaching English is described. Using the Challenge method, students become accustomed to finding solutions to problems and implementing them, identifying topics that are difficult for students to learn. Once the problem is identified, students formulate questions, the answers of which bring them closer to solving the problem. The guiding questions identified by the learners help to determine what knowledge is needed to solve the problem and to map the knowledge. Students determine what lessons, lectures, resources are needed to solve the problem. This method considers the effective teaching of English. Students learn the language in accordance with social and communicative skills, while the main focus in the acquisition of language is a thorough and intensive learning.

Keywords: challenge, communication, interactive teaching methods, intensive training, English.

CHALLENGE ТӘСІЛІН АҒЫЛШЫН ТІЛІН ОҚЫТУДА ҚОЛДАНУ ТИІМДІЛІГІ

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АҢДАТПА

Мақалада ағылшын тілін оқытуда қолданатын тиімді әдістерге әдеби шолу жасалынды. Қазіргі таңда ағылшын тілі әлемдік деңгейдегі мүмкіндіктерге жол ашатын негізгі инструмент болып табылады. Мақала мақсаты заман талабына сай заманауи әдістердің ерекшеліктерімен тиімділігін зерттеу. Білім алушыларға оқыту барысында когнитивті процестердің дамуына сай тиімді әдістерді анықтау. Challenge тәсілі тәуелсіз шешім қабылдау дағдыларын дамыту, тіл үйрену барысында топтық немесе индивидуалды жұмыс барысында әртүрлі коммуникативті дағдыларды қалыптастыру. Challenge тәсілін ағылшын тілін оқыту барысында қолданудың тиімділігі сипатталады. Challenge тәсілін қолдана отырып оқыту барысындағы білім алушыларға қиындық туғызатын тақырыптарды анықтай отырып, мәселенің шешімін тауып, оны жүзеге асыруға дағдыланады. Мәселе анықталғаннан кейін білім алушылар сұрақтарын тұжырымдайды, олардың жауаптары оларды мәселені шешуге жақындатады. Білім алушылар анықтаған бағыттаушы сұрақтар проблеманы шешу үшін қандай білім қажет екенін анықтауға және білімді картаға түсіруге көмектеседі. Студенттер мәселені шешу үшін қандай сабақтар, дәрістер, ресурстар қажет болатынын анықтайды. Бұл тәсіл арқылы ағылшын тілін тиімді оқытудың қарастырылады. Білім алушылар тілі меңгеру барысында жетік және интенсивті оқытуды басты назарға алса, тіл үйреуді әлеуметтік, коммуникативті дағдыларға сай меңгереді.

Кілт сөздері: challenge, қарым-қатынас, интерактивті оқыту әдістері, қарқынды оқыту, ағылшын тілі.

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ МЕТОДА CHALLENGE В ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

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В статье представлено литературный обзор эффективных методик обучения английскому языку. Сегодня английский язык – главный инструмент доступа к возможностям мирового уровня. Цель статьи - изучить особенности и эффективность современных методов в соответствии с современными требованиями. Выявить эффективные методы развития познавательных процессов в обучении студентов. Метод Challenge – это развитие навыков самостоятельного принятия решений, формирование различных коммуникативных навыков в групповой или индивидуальной работе при изучении языка. Описана эффективность использования метода Challenge в обучении английскому языку. Используя метод Challenge, обучающиеся привыкают находить решения проблем и реализовывать их, выявляя темы, которые им сложно усвоить. После определения проблемы обучающиеся формулируют вопросы, ответы на которые приближают их к решению проблемы. Направляющие вопросы, задаваемые обучающимся, помогают определить, какие знания необходимы для решения проблемы, и сопоставить эти знания. Студенты определяют, какие уроки, лекции, ресурсы необходимы для решения задачи. Такой метод предполагает эффективное обучение английскому языку. Студенты изучают язык в соответствии с социальными и коммуникативными навыками, при этом основное внимание в процессе овладения языком уделяется тщательному и интенсивному обучению.

Ключевые слова: challenge, общение, интерактивные методы обучения, интенсивное обучение, английский язык.

The 21st century is one of the requirements and unique for learning foreign languages. Learning a foreign (English) language is not only about respecting fashion or someone's will, but also the process of obtaining a vital education in a modern society developing towards globalization.

In modern conditions, English is a world science and advanced technology, global politics, economics, trade and transport language. About 80% of all information is stored there, more than 50% of websites on the Internet in English. World science is monolingual, since up to 70% of general scientific publications and 99% of publications in the natural sciences are published in English [1].

In 2016, according to various statistical indicators, the number of national-English bilinguals from 603 163.010 to 1 billion people significantly exceeded the number of native speakers— consist of 339 370 920 people. This study characterizes the features of Challenge's approach to teaching English.

Teaching foreign languages is one of the difficult and urgent problems in modern society. Currently, great attention needs to be paid to the development of methods and methods of teaching English. Teaching methods and methods are one of the most important components of the educational process. Systematic training is necessary without applying appropriate methods. Indeed, effectively shaping the learning process gives the learner an advantage in language learning. Therefore, the educational side, researchers, should take into account the difficulties of learning a language that meet modern requirements, the level of education of the population. The effectiveness of language learning using the challenge method, the student independently formed skills to solve difficulties in language learning, search and creative qualities develop

The Challenge method is effective in teaching English. In accordance with it, the tasks are:

1. Determination of the meaning of methods and methods of teaching a foreign language
2. Determination of the effectiveness of the challenge method in teaching English;
3. Improving the effectiveness of these methods and approaches through training proof.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Challenge is an educational approach based on solving specific issues. The method is the basis of training in solving specific global problems. This circle is characterized by a combination of joint and practical parts that allow you to identify ideas, ask good questions, identify and solve difficulties, gain deep knowledge of discipline, develop skills of the 21st century, from all participants (students, teachers, families and members of society) [2, 23 b.].

Participants in the educational process receive a practical task before gaining knowledge of the studied object. Working together to solve this problem, participants analyze the question, share thoughts, create a hypothesis, study additional information and choose the optimal solutions. Acquisition of new knowledge and skills, appear in the process of mastering new knowledge and skills, finding options and making decisions.

Unlike the traditional method of obtaining knowledge in the audience, that is, in conditions of isolation from practice, problem-oriented training focuses students on a state in which they have to make specific decisions and achieve a certain result, teaches effective polling and creativity of each situation [3, 88.].

The Challenge method appeared in the project “Apple Classroom of Tomorrow – Today” (2008), initiated by Apple, Inc in ACOT2 to determine important principles for designing the educational environment of the 21st century (Apple Inc., 2008). Starting with the principles of design, the team of Apple, Inc, together with exemplary educators, provides training, testing and training based on difficulties.

The Challenge’s range of methods is divided into three stages:

Participation is a process of raising an important question in which students move from an abstract big idea to a concrete and practical one.

Research - all students plan and consider the effectiveness of the use, application of materials that form the basis of solutions and meet academic requirements.

An act is a motivated decision that is prepared and implemented together with a real audience, after which it is evaluated based on the results [4,12 b].

Features of the Challenge method:

- Raising questions is a starting point in mastering new knowledge and skills.
- Students are responsible for solving the problem.
- The role of the teacher is to moderate the search and analysis of information, coordinate the attack on the brain and group discussions. In addition, this stimulates the critical thinking of students and the search for their optimal solutions.
- Students actively participate in group work and search for joint solutions.
- When solving this problem, students will receive new knowledge and skills [items 5, 23].

To solve the problem, participants need to find information, analyze it, initiate a number of initiatives, analyze alternatives and choose the best option. The difficulties that students receive in completing this task push them to independently search for the necessary knowledge and tools, stimulate creativity and critical thinking.

Under certain conditions, the acquisition of knowledge and skills close to specific conditions increases the effectiveness of training and its practical value.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Setting a theme that makes it difficult to learn English to the Challenge method is the starting point for mastering new knowledge and skills.

Each question implies different solutions. The decision should be carefully, clearly, clearly formulated and implemented in the local community [6, 25].

It is very important to start checking after you find your solutions. The focus group needs to create a prototype or present a solution. The decision is made by the students and is carried out by them independently, the method determines the possibilities and creativity of the students. Once a solution is selected, it is important to plan the implementation of the solution and schedule the time.

A video recording of the decision, a big idea for society, a question in the field of public education, tells about the problem, after which they bring to the attention of a video message or written information about how they solved the problem and how the group came to a solution [7, article 69].

Students evaluate the effectiveness of the solution by implementing it.

The results of students' decisions are recorded using quantitative and qualitative methods. Determine the effectiveness of their decisions and subsequent steps.

The most important point is the reflection on the path traveled, which will help consolidate the experience. During the discussion, they will discuss what difficulties the listeners faced, what knowledge and skills were useful, what is the path of further development.

Each step must be written, and at the end - given to a duplicate in the form of a working publication [8, article 69].

Formal and informal assessment is carried out throughout the process and should assess the knowledge, skills of students and the process of solving problems itself. The future of teachers and students about how perceptions are assessed and controlled is determined on both sides. To reveal the main topic of this study, it is necessary to note the complexity of the methodology for teaching the vocabulary of English. It is necessary to conceptually cover a certain direction regarding learning, teaching an English-language dictionary fund for other language students. Thus, the conceptual scope includes: the definition of a vocabulary term, types of vocabulary, the importance of the vocabulary fund, the general principles of successful training of the vocabulary fund, the complexity of teaching English in the context of a foreign language, the methodology of teaching a dictionary and the need for teaching vocabulary. To carry out this study, the researchers, after familiarizing themselves with the well-known literature, asked certain questions and conducted many previous studies.

As a general fact, qualitative research methods are designed to help uncover the behavior and perception of the target audience by referencing a specific topic. There are usually qualitative research methods such as in-depth dialogue, focus groups,

ethnographic research, content analysis, situational research. The results of qualitative methods are descriptive and conclusions can be drawn from the information obtained. The following are the most commonly used qualitative research methods: individual dialogue focus groups, ethnographic studies, situational studies, control process and office work. From these quantitative methods, the researchers chose a clerical method. As a data source, this method uses already existing trusted documents and similar information sources. This data can be used in a new study, in particular, the integration of materials created by old sources of information in accordance with modern requirements. Collection of data that can be used in the course of the study

CONCLUSION

The research studied the question of methods and methods of teaching foreign languages. The history of the release and the features of supporting the Challenge method are presented. Knowledge of the nature of the methods is very important both for the scientific justification of the technique and for the application of its data in educational practice. The secret of effective learning lies, first of all, in the essence of teaching methods. The method always implies the actions of the student with the student aimed at solving practical and educational issues. The Challenge method aims to create an emphasis on the main problems encountered in learning English. With this method, group and individual training can be developed. The main features of the method are creativity, work on specific issues.

The formation of modern training programs is the main goal of each teacher. A teacher using the challenge method can work to increase the motivation of the student. By raising interest, he may become interested in society. At the heart are questions of language learning. After the question is clarified, work is carried out using certain specially created steps. The identified question after the decision must be published as a duplicate. The published duplication will contribute to reducing the main barriers to language proficiency for both society and students [para. 10, 325].

The Challenge method can be used not only when using a student, but also for a student by purpose. By the method, the student solves the questions that arise from him. Traditional learning integration through the Challenge method is one of the most pressing topics and unique at present. In the event of major difficulties in learning English, it is possible to increase the rate of development of cognitive processes occurring along the personality using the Challenge method [11, 77].

Special attention of Methodists and teachers is paid to communicative and intensive methods, as well as active teaching methods. By uniting, they solve the most pressing problems of modern education. The main goal is to develop the thinking (speech and thought) abilities of students, memorize and over-memorize many foreign language materials, as well as take into account the motives of learning, interpersonal relations in

the group, the abilities of schoolchildren and increase the level of their language training.

High mobility and the development of methods enrich the theory and practice of training with new effective method, make it possible to predict the paths of new research and discoveries at a certain level.

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